

Design and Development of a Microcontroller Based Stadiometer

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and construction of a portable stadiometer for human measurements for up to approximately 200cm, with the use of microcontroller and ultrasonic sensor device (transducer). Ultrasonic transducers use ultrasound waves having frequencies greater than the upper limit of human hearing. The ultrasonic transducer is controlled by the PIC16F877A microcontroller to generate an ultrasound wave to be emitted through the transmitter, and the pulse is reflected off an object and the echo received by the receiver, derive the time traveled, calculate the distance, and then calculate the height which is then displayed on the Liquid Crystal Display. The use of the ultrasound wave finds its application in several sectors such as in the medical, industrial and security, electronic and navigational sectors.

Keyword: Stadiometer, microcontroller, ultrasound wave, ultrasonic device.

INTRODUCTION

Human height is defined as the distance from the bottom of the feet to the peak of the head in a human body, while standing erect. It could be measured in centimeter (metric system) [1,2], and feet and inches (imperial system) [3,4]. On the average males are taller than females.

several places such as medical centers, screening centers, military offices etc.

For height measurements, the following instructions are considered [6];

- ❖ Remove shoes, hat, and hair ornaments, buns, braids to extent possible.
- ❖ Stand on the footplate or uncarpeted floor with back against stadiometer rule.
- ❖ Bring legs together, ensure legs are straight, arms are at sides, and shoulders are relaxed.
- ❖ Assure the back of the body touches/has contact with the stadiometer at some point, preferably with heels, buttocks, upper back and head touching the measuring surface.
- ❖ Ensure that the body is in a straight line (mid-axillary line parallel to the stadiometer).
- ❖ Ensure the head is in the appropriate position (Frankfort plane).
- ❖ Breathe in and hold breath while being measured.

Height measurement is important when monitoring health and growth. Height measurements coupled with weight measurements are used to calculate the Body Mass Index, BMI, a measure of body fat, that is, the ratio of the weight of the body in kilograms to the square of its height in meters. Height measurements and follow-up is necessary for the detection of abnormalities that may affect the normal growth rate in human. It is used to collect accurate height data of people and to help

short nurses who could not accurately record height information for tall persons.

Accurate height measurements help in the monitoring of height for any defect or factors that might affect growth.

Manual height measuring devices (Stadiometers) give inaccurate readings and constantly require calibration services which are expensive; therefore the use of electronic stadiometers such as the microcontroller based height measuring devices turn out to be more reliable. Time management is another problem since it takes a substantial amount of time to process a lot of people's measurement.

Table 1 Average height in Nigeria [5]

Features	Values
Average male height	163.8cm
Average female height	157.8
Stature ratio (male to female)	1.04
Sample population / Age range	18-74
Methodology	Measured
Year	1994 – 1996

Basic Overview of the Unit

The block diagram for the microcontroller based stadiometer is shown below (figure 2.). The major components in the designing of the microcontroller based stadiometer are the PIC16F877A Microcontroller, ultrasonic sensor device (transducer), and the Liquid crystal display (LCD).

The Ultrasonic Sensor Device (Transducer)

Ultrasonic sensors (also known as transceivers when they both send and receive but more generally called transducers) work on a principle similar to radar or sonar, which evaluates attributes of a target by interpreting the echoes from radio or sound waves respectively. Active ultrasonic sensors generate

high frequency sound waves and evaluate the echo which is received back by the sensor, measuring the time interval between sending the signal and receiving the echo to determine the distance to an object or matter. Passive ultrasonic sensors are basically microphones that detect ultrasonic noise that is present under certain conditions. Technology is limited by the shapes of surfaces and the density or consistency of the material. Foam, in particular, can distort surface level readings [7].

The PIC Microcontroller (PIC16F877A)

This is a powerful (200 nanosecond instruction execution) yet easy-to-program (only 35 single word instructions) CMOS FLASH-based 8-bit microcontroller.

Figure 2. Block Diagram of the Microcontroller Based standiometer

The microcontroller has architecture of 40 pin package and is upwards compatible with the PIC16C5X, PIC12CXXX and PIC16C7X devices. The PIC16F877A features 256 bytes of EEPROM data memory, self programming, an ICD, 2 Comparators, 8 channels of 10-bit Analog-to-Digital (A/D) converter, 2 capture/compare/PWM functions, the synchronous serial port can be configured as either 3-wire Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI™) or the 2-wire Inter-Integrated Circuit (I²C™) bus and a Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter (USART). All of these features make it ideal for more advanced level applications in automotive, industrial, appliances and consumer applications [8].

The Liquid Crystal Display (LCD)

A liquid-crystal display (LCD) is a flat panel display, electronic visual display, or video display that uses the light modulating properties of liquid crystals. Liquid crystals do not emit light directly.

LCDs are used in a wide range of applications including computer monitors, televisions, instrument panels, aircraft cockpit displays, and signage. They are common in consumer devices such as DVD players, gaming devices, clocks, watches, calculators, and telephones, and have replaced cathode ray tube (CRT) displays in most applications. They are available in a wider range of screen sizes than CRT and plasma displays, and since they do not use phosphors, they do not suffer image burn-in. LCDs are, however, susceptible to image persistence [9].

DESIGN CONSIDERATION

Hardware Description

The hardware description describes the principle of operation of the circuit diagram in figure 3.

The concept of the stadiometer device is based on the measurement of distance with the use of an ultrasonic sensor device controlled by a microcontroller. The stadiometer device is to be placed at a fixed height 'H' of 200cm (2m) above the reference level.

The microcontroller being the heart of the device triggers the ultrasonic sensor device. Once the trigger is being received by the ultrasonic sensor device, the sensor emits ultrasound wave in a linear direction towards the obstacle (in this case, the plank on top of the head) and awaits the reception of echo which is being reflected by the obstacle. Upon reception of the echo the time 'T_t' between pulse emission and echo reception is being derived by the microcontroller in the Timer0 module. The derived time 'T_t' is further divided by two (2), because the time needed is the time it takes the pulse to hit obstacle. Dividing the 'T_t' by two yields time 'T'. The derived time T is then multiplied by the speed of sound in air (340 m/s) to calculate the distance 'd' from the ultrasonic device to the obstacle (the plank on top of the head). Once the distance 'd' is calculated, the height 'h' of the person standing under the stadiometer device is derived by subtracting the distance 'd' from the fixed height 'H'.

$$T_t = \text{total time for emission and reception of pulse.}$$

$$\text{derived time } T = \frac{T_t}{2}$$

$$= \text{Time traveled in respect to one direction}$$

$$\text{Calculated distance } d$$

$$= \text{speed of sound in air (340 m/s)}$$

$$\times \text{derived time } T$$

So,

$$\text{Calculated height } h = H - d$$

$$= 200\text{cm} - d$$

With the height calculated and derived it is displayed on the LCD. Sending of trigger pulses and also the calculation of height is done by the microcontroller at regular intervals in a never ending cycle. The microcontroller is programmed with a portion of code that reads the status of the hold button whether high (logic 1) or low (logic 0). If the status of the button is high, it executes a subroutine which holds the result of the last measured height on the screen for 10 seconds after which it relieves the microcontroller into going back to its normal operation.

Figure 3 Circuit diagram of Stadiometer

Software Description

The operation of the program is summarized as follows:

BEGIN

- Initialize I/O ports
- Initialize LCD
- Send start-up message to the LCD

DO FOREVER

- Send a pulse to the ultrasonic module
- Start timer
- Wait until echo pulse is received
- Calculate the elapsed time
- Divide the time by 2 to find the time to the object
- Calculate the distance to the object
- Calculate the height of the person
- Display the height of the person on the LCD
- If button pressed, wait for 10 seconds

END DO

END

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The sensitivity and accuracy of the device have been tested for height measurement and compared to a measurement made on the wall for height measurement.

Table 4. Compared Results From The Stadiometer And Wall Mount Readings For Adults.

Stadiometer Reading (X ₁)	Wall Reading (X ₂)	Differences (X ₁ - X ₂)	(X ₁ - X ₂) ²
179.2	179	0.2	0.04
181.24	181	0.24	0.0576
182.1	182	0.1	0.01
183.04	183	0.04	0.0016
170.64	170.5	0.14	0.0196
160.4	161	0.4	0.16
166.67	166.5	0.17	0.0289
164.56	164.3	0.26	0.0676
			$\sum(X_1 - X_2)^2 = 0.3853$

Table 5 Compared Results From The Stadiometer And Wall Mount Readings For Children.

Stadiometer Reading (X ₁)	Wall Reading (X ₂)	Differences (X ₁ - X ₂)	(X ₁ - X ₂) ²
62.94	64.8	-1.86	3.4596
80.36	82.3	-1.94	3.7636
70.14	72	-1.86	3.4596
121.03	121.5	-0.47	0.2209
83.62	85.5	-1.88	3.5344
111.71	113.3	-1.59	2.5281
94.23	95.5	-1.27	1.6129
104.62	106	-1.38	1.9044
			$\sum(X_1 - X_2)^2 = 20.4835$

From Table 4. root-mean-square error (RSME) or root-mean-square deviation (RSMD) can be calculated to determine the accuracy for taking measurements for adults.

$$(RMSE) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(X_1 - X_2)^2}{N}}$$

$$(RMSE)_{for\ Adult} = \sqrt{\frac{0.3853}{8}}$$

$$(RMSE)_{for\ Adult} = 0.2194596$$

From Table 5 root-mean-square error (RSME) or root-mean-square deviation (RSMD) can be calculated to determine the accuracy for taking measurements for children.

$$(RMSE) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(X_1 - X_2)^2}{N}}$$

$$(RMSE)_{for\ children} = \sqrt{\frac{20.4835}{8}}$$

$$(RMSE)_{for\ children} = 1.600137$$

DISCUSSION

During the course of installing the stadiometer device and taking of measurements some challenges were encountered and noted, one of which is getting the exact placement of 200cm. any fault in the placement of the device will affect the accuracy

of the calculated height. So also, during the process of taking measurements it was noted that some of the readings were incorrect due to the fact that the incident ultrasound wave not properly reflected back to the ultrasonic device. In the case of people with much hair on the head, the hair tends to absorb the ultrasound wave or scatter the reflection which affects the accuracy of the reading on the stadiometer device. In other to solve this issue, a plastic plank has been provided to be placed on top of the head to aid proper reflection of the transmitted pulse back to the ultrasonic sensor device and increases the accuracy of the stadiometer device.

So also, during the period of taking measurements for children, it was noted that a tolerance of about 1.6% occurred. The occurrence of high tolerance compared to that of the measurements taken for adults is due to the increase in the distance between the ultrasonic sensor device and the peak of the head or the plank to be placed on the head. Therefore, it could be said that device is most accurate in measuring Adults.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This work has successfully presented a functional and accurate portable microcontroller based stadiometer, with automation, reliability and even LCD output display.

It is recommended that future work should improve on the stadiometer design by adding voice automation, weight measurement to provide results for BMI (Body Mass Index), also adding the designed device to a computer system to automatically store the measured height and in monitoring height or growth.

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